

Occupational Therapy (OT) is, according to the definition of the World Health Organization (WHO), “the set of techniques, methods and actions that, through activities applied for therapeutic purposes, prevents and maintains health, favors the restoration of function, makes up for the disabling deficits and values the behavioral assumptions and their profound significance to achieve the greatest possible independence and reintegration of the individual in all its aspects: labor, mental, physical and social”.

Bridgeview Nursing Home, [nursing home and rehabilitation center](#), located in Bridgeview, Illinois provides occupational therapy to its residents.

According to experts from Bridgeview Nursing Home, sometimes the literal translation of the term Occupational Therapy leads to confusing the purpose of this discipline with the intention of keeping the person busy or entertaining. Therefore, Bridgeview Nursing Home experts note that it is important to note that the purpose of OT is to achieve the maximum functionality of the person with some type of limitation, be it physical, cognitive, behavioral or a variety of them, through meaningful activity and / or workshops. therapeutic with both general and specific objectives.

The professionals from [Bridgeview Nursing Home](#), who provide occupational therapy, are endowed with socio-health knowledge encompassed within the field of rehabilitation, which allow intervention in three areas: self-maintenance, productivity and leisure of the person and also provide the professional with the ability to:

- Make an assessment of the capabilities and limitations of the person. (With the different batteries of the service).
- Prevent disabilities (imbalances, occupational dysfunctions, anticipate possible injuries and pathologies).
- Carry out an assessment of sensory, superior, social and psychological capacities.
- Develop and evaluate rehabilitation treatment programs with their corresponding individualized objectives.
- Obtain the involvement of the patient in their own treatment.
- Train and re-educate in the basic and instrumental activities of daily life.
- Train the use of technical aids whenever and wherever necessary, compensating for their limitations.
- Prepare and carry out the prescription of orthoses, prostheses and technical aids, as well as the training of the person in their use.
- Adapt the environment and develop programs to eliminate architectural barriers. Advise families, users and professionals of other specialties.
- Evaluate the means of transport and their possible adaptations.
- Train the individual to achieve the highest degree of socio-labor reintegration possible as an active member within their community.
- Help the individual readjust her daily habits.
- Reinsertion of the individual in their daily life and in the midst of it in the best possible conditions.
- Collaborate with public and / or private institutions for the promotion and development of intervention programs for the disabled population.

Bridgeview Nursing Home provides round-the-clock supervision with meals, health management, [various types of therapy](#) and a range of support for their residents.

